
Research

Critical investigation on the role of corporate social responsibility in business expansion: The case study of Grameen Bank

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Abstract: CSR has become a hot topic in academic and business circles. This discussion acknowledges CSR's importance in the first world but challenges whether developing-world organizations have CSR commitments. CSR is increasingly relevant to corporations in developed countries due to higher public expectations of responsible behavior. In poor countries, social expectations are based on financial success, hence CSR is of minimal importance to individuals and enterprises. CSR is a new concept in Bangladesh, and many organizations try to balance it with other duties. The banking sector in Bangladesh has a long history of engaging in CSR activities like assisting various organizations, beautifying the state, and sponsoring cultural events. In recent years, this envelopment has made great progress since 2008, when the Bangladesh Bank Guideline recommended banks to be more organized. Business exists to make money. Profit-seeking is sometimes considered immoral since it emphasizes self-interest. Self-interest is not selfishness, which prioritizes one's own well-being over others'. Self-interest is only concerned with monetary gain and is vital for society's productivity and asset management (Safety & Rights Society, 2014). Profit rewards hard labor and ingenuity, which most people want because it would be illogical to save and invest otherwise. Business organizations can't function properly without society's help. Businesses should assume social duties because they have the resources to do so. Business has some of the world's brightest ideas and great financial resources. Businesses should produce social and economic capital to "improve the world." In recent years, several businesses have suffered setbacks and even banks have gone bankrupt due to inadequate shareholder supervision. Shareholders and other stakeholders are increasingly looking for increased transparency and accountability of their businesses to ensure growth and that the business will continue to exist in the foreseeable future, not only in terms of maximizing shareholder wealth but also taking into account the needs of other stakeholders (consumers, employees, suppliers, government, etc.). Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is an intrinsic aspect of long-term company and sustainable growth and success. It promotes values locally and globally and is a developed-country phenomenon. As a result, a large body of literature on organizational social structure has emerged in developed countries. CSR assures firms will act morally and contribute to the financial prosperity of the people while enhancing the lives of employees and the local public. CSR is vital for organizations' sustainability worldwide. CSR is a global concern and all organizations practice it. In this research, the authors discuss CSR and examine the well-being of certain state-owned and private commercial banks in Bangladesh. "Bangladesh Bank" has recommended commercial banks to contribute to people's well-being. Many businesses and banks have failed in recent years. In recent years, CSR has grown increasingly significant. This thesis examines CSR's role in corporate growth. It also discusses CSR and how it might boost business growth. Grameen Bank (GB), a Bangladeshi bank, was chosen as a case study due to its success and expansion over the years, especially throughout the financial crisis. We're interested in CSR's part in this success. This work will examine the visibility of CSR in a bank like GB that has diverged from standard patterns and how this has affected its growth.

Grameen Bank does some CSR. Grameen Bank's CSR is different from typical banks due to its nature (social business). Disclosure of financial information, auditing of accounts and constant rotation of auditors, remuneration structure of the managing director designed so he gets no extra benefit for taking excessive risk by lending to unworthy customers (here we're talking about customers that do not belong to a credit group), and credit risk monitoring by lending money only to customers belonging to a credit group and giving out big loans to creditworthy customers are all examples of CSR in the UK. Disclosure promotes depositor and stakeholder confidence, auditing adds legitimacy to financial statements and further increases depositor confidence and GB reliability, credit risk monitoring As a matter of ethics and faith, not rationality, Grameen bank lends to persons without collateral and promotes repayment by granting larger loans only after smaller ones are repaid. All these boost business growth. Corporate governance helps GB grow and expand.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility ,Business Expansion, Grameen Bank, Education CSR Initiative, Leadership Development Programs, Financial Literacy and Access, Environmental Initiative.

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Introduction

Background of the study

In created financial aspects the idea of business has changed from benefit making exercises to social welfare exercises where organizations are mindful to it's investors as well as to the majority of its partners (Islam 2012). CSR (Corporate Social Responsibilities) is generally another idea in Bangladesh and every one of the establishments attempt to keep up this obligation alongside different duties.

In Bangladesh, the managing an account division has a heavenly history of getting connected with themselves in various types of social exercises which is formally known as CSR like gifts to various associations, nation beautification, belittling social exercises and so on. Be that as it may, in some ongoing years there is gigantic development in this contribution, in light of the fact that in 2008 Bangladesh Bank Guideline proposed the Banks to include in these exercises in a more organized manner. This paper in fundamentally centered around the CSR exercises of the bank and how it is connected with business development and in what degree Banks are anxious to include in these kind of CSR exercises. Banks are benefit based associations, so in this point of view they most likely need to burn through cash in those segments which will straightforwardly or in a roundabout way bring cash for them, so clearly there are some positive connections among CSR and banks gainfulness. To break down the job of Corporate Social Responsibility in business development Grameen Bank(GB) has been pick. Grameen Bank received the arrangement of adding to the social reason since its origin in 1996. Amid the most recent 22 years it has been proceeding with its exertion as a pioneer in the keeping money division and has turned into the pioneer much in front of alternate banks. The bank likewise needs to dispense with the inappropriateness in the general public, to make individual inclination among the natives of the nation, spur individuals to do acts of kindness and preserve nature. Hence instruction, medicinal services,

human asset advancement, protection of nature, making of social mindfulness, restoration of down and out individuals, correspondence and address human sufferings emerging out of artificial and regular causes are a portion of the imperative regions where the Bank has been doing its social and magnanimous exercises.

Numerous organizations have endured genuine difficulties as of late and a few banks have even gone bankrupt because of deficient checking of a few partners of such organizations. These days, investors and different partners are progressively paying special mind to expand straightforwardness and responsibility (Mallin, 2010) of their organizations with the end goal to guarantee that there are prospects for development and that the business will keep on existing in the fore seeable future, as far as amplifying investor's riches as well as mulling over the necessities of different partners required with the business (like, customers, workers, providers, government and so forth) one reason why Corporate Social Responsibility have progressively turned out to be essential over the most recent couple of years.

The motivation behind this examination is to analyze the pretended by CSR in business development by taking a gander at how great CSR can be accomplished and how it can realize development in a business. The theory will adopt a contextual investigation strategy and we will look at CSR practice in Grameen Bank (GB). I picked this bank since it has recorded gigantic achievement and development throughout the years even amidst the fierce monetary emergency, despite everything it stood up unshaken, so we wish to discover the role of CSR played in this achievement basically. The normal commitments of this work will be to see the permeability of CSR in a bank like GB which has veered off from regular managing an account model and how this has impacted its development. The postulation will likewise give a short knowledge of CSR in social organizations by and large and this might be of assistance for future research around there.

Problem statement

Organizations are surrounded by environments which impact their works and access to limited natural resources, that is, raw materials, skilled workers, network, technological knowhow and customers" supports (Barney, 1991). Businesses mainly focus on internal factors, such as profits and growth, but not on stakeholder"s benefits which are the supporting keys to business growth (Carroll & Shabana, 2010). One of the major concerns facing the modern organization centers around the question of how they can continue to grow profits, increase innovations and expand across geographic markets, while taking on the additional responsibilities and pressures that go along with CSR (Mackey & Tyson, 2007).

"The current business environment is abuzz with issues related to sustainable development which is an idea of ensuring better quality of life which aims to protect the environment, enhance social progress, use natural resources prudently and maintain high and stable economic growth" (Chakraborty, 2010). CSR is believed to have a significant influence on organization sustainability. In the business context, CSR has emerged as a form of sustainability governance with advantages to the economic, environment and social progress (Galbreath, 2010). Companies are aware that they can contribute to sustainable development by managing their operations in such a way that they enhance economic growth and increase competitiveness besides protecting environment and being committed to social responsibilities (Gerry and Scholes, 2005). A key direct contribution of CSR to organization growth is its contribution to marketing and building organization image (Kiura, 2011). Therefore, growth in business cannot be achieved solely by profit maximization but through responsible behavior and market orientation. There is a growing realization that businesses cannot succeed in isolation and social progress is a necessity for sustainable growth to be realized, though the contribution of CSR on growth exists only in theory and is yet to be clearly quantified.

In the last two decades, CSR application among the Bangladeshi corporations has grown exponentially with the need to satisfy this unwritten law that organizations should work within a CSR framework (Wanyama 2012). Gerry and Scholes (2005) observed that the link between CSR and corporate performance can only be clear if the components of the CSR programmes in an organization are clearly identified before the relationship of the joint functions can be

established. Among these firms adopting CSR is Grameen Bank, one of the largest financial institutions in the country. The growth of Grameen Bank in Bangladesh and into the South Asian region has been widely linked with the bank's involvement in CSR activities, though no scientific review has yet been undertaken to confirm this assertion. Fombrun et al. (2000) argues that a corporation's improvement in investors' trust, new market opportunities and positive reactions of capital markets can only be realized through involvement of CSR performance by continuously monitoring internal and external events and trends so that the required changes can be made as needed. Galbreath (2010) asserts that the conceptual links between strategic management practices and CSR performance have little or no empirical verification and therefore its impact on firm performance is mythical rather than factual. This study will be assessing CSR performance against growth and might find links within this phenomenon. Pohle and Hittner (2008), postulated ways in which CSR undertakings can be aligned to institutional growth, though they never got to determine the value of this postulated growth.

Whereas many studies on CSR (Kiura, 2011; Ratichek, 2011; Wanyama 2012; Auka, 2006; Porter and Kramer, 2006; Galbreath 2010; Mackey & Tyson, 2007; and, Marsiglia & Falautano 2005) have focused on the activities involved and their benefits to CSR targeted stakeholders as the consumers, employees and society in general, they have left out the impact of CSR on firm performance and growth. On the other hand, studies done that link organization growth to CSR only bring out the expectance of firm growth which is conceptualized as indirect. Therefore, even though the topic of growth and CSR has received a wide interest within scholarly circles, it is not yet fully understood and clearly quantified. More so is the case of Bangladesh where very few studies have been done in relation to CSR and Business Expansion. This study therefore bridged this gap by assessing the role of CSR on the expansion of Grameen Bank .

Research questions

The questions that this research aims to answer are shown as following: "What are the impacts of Corporate Social Responsibility on business expansion ?" Based on the main question, there are some sub questions developed to answer the question more specifically:

1. Why does Grameen Bank undertake CSR activities?
2. What are the Key CSR activities of Grameen Bank?
3. Which among different CSR levels has the strongest influence on business expansion?

Research objective

The main objective of the study is "Explain how CSR is related with business expansion in the banking sector with special reference to Grameen Bank" the study should also share some light on the following matters –

- To investigate the key CSR activities of Grameen Bank
- To study the theories and guidelines for CSR practices in Bangladeshi Banking Sector.
 - To study the CSR practices as per GRI(Global Reporting Initiative)guidelines being implemented by Bangladeshi banking sector.
- To offer recommendations for better CSR practices based on findings from this study.

Purpose of the study

- a) Research

The study will contribute to building a body of knowledge in literature for further research. Secondly, the outcome of the research will also serve as a reference resource for other researchers to investigate further into areas that this study will not cover.

- b) Practice

It will also contribute slightly to the stakeholders understanding of the mutual benefits that come out of CSR for both the corporations and firms and also influence their decisions on investing in banking sectors.

c) Policy

It will also be used by researchers and policy makers in the area of CSR as far as the banking sector in Bangladesh is concerned.

Justification of the study

The study generated useful information both in theory and in practice. The findings are beneficial to policy makers, bank managers, members of the public who are the customers of the banks and the government.

To the bank managers, the study generated helpful findings on the impacts of corporate social responsibility on the growth of an organization. This information may be used to make decisions on the adoption of CSR projects and the strategies to adopt them, more so to the management and the cross-functional CSR strategy teams at Grameen Bank.

The findings outline the associated benefits of the CSR activities to the financial institutions. This helps institutions to choose the best CSR activities that benefits members of the especially the bank customers. With financial institutions instituting CSR activities as strategic response, the study provides members of public with an understanding of the value of CSR and hence offers their support for the project.

The study adds value to the existing theories on technology. It serves as a source of reference to the future scholars and academicians in their future research. Other scholars use the information gathered to expound on areas not yet addressed in CSR and corporate strategy, while the study's findings offers reference materials for them while replicating the study elsewhere. Furthermore, although CSR literature is widely available, there is a recurring criticism that it lacks empirical support, thus weakening its validity, but this study reclaims this validity.

Scope and study limitations

This study aimed to find out the impact of corporate social responsibility on the Expansion of Grameen Bank in Bangladesh. This was a descriptive study covering all the firm's CSR undertakings in Bangladesh by assessing their CSR initiatives and their growth. CSR initiatives were measured by both financial and perception levels while growth on the other hand was measured by the changes in customer levels (market share), number of employee base, number of outlets and profits. The study also reviewed available empirical studies to help provide more insights on CSR relationship to economic growth or business expansion . The study was limited to this scope and only dwelt on Grameen Bank case and only in relation to CSR and business expansion, though other issues might have seemed relevant to the study.

The study faced some limitations. Some respondents at Grameen Bank were reluctant to divulge the required information for the study which posed a big challenge. The study therefore made use of secondary data to improve on reliability.

Research methodology

Research hypothesis

This section will explain about the hypothesis development. After reviewing literature review and lots of existing research journal, it has been decided in this research to choose five independent variables such as Education Initiatives, Leadership Program, Financial literacy & Access, Agricultural Support, Environment Protection as they affect the dependent variable which is the expansion of the company or Business Expansion .

The relationship between CSR and Business expansion

First, the previous studies on CSR and corporate performance are reviewed. A number of such studies indicated that CSR and corporate performance are positively related. Waddock and Graves (1997) developed two hypotheses

concerning the relationship between CSR and corporate performance: 1) if the corporate performance is good, CSR will be addressed (the slack resource hypothesis); 2) the company will see good earnings as a result of addressing CSR (the good management hypothesis). Through the analysis of data from a US firm, the relationship between CSR and corporate performance is found to be positive in both directions. According to McGuire et al. (1988), the business results greatly influence the extent to which a CSR policy is followed, meaning that consideration is given primarily to financial results and then to social responsibility. Moreover, in terms of the relationship between CSR and business results, they found that CSR is not directly linked to subsequent strong business results, but that risk is reduced first and this then leads to high financial results in the future. Orlitzky et al. (2003) undertook a meta-analysis of approximately 52 empirical studies performed in relation to sociality, such as environmental countermeasures and financial business results, in the 30 years following the 1970s. According to this study, there is a significant positive correlation between financial business results, Price earnings and societal or environmental performance; the results also verify the existence of mutually complementary cause-effect relationships on the basis of a time series analysis. On the other hand, Mahapatra (1984) and Jaggi and Freedman (1992), amongst others, found a negative relationship between CSR and corporate performance. According to Mahapatra (1984), eco-management (or social responsibility) and financial business results are negatively related. Aupperle et al.'s (1985) study indicated that CSR and corporate performance are not related. Similarly, Ullman (1985) observed no significant trend between CSR and corporate performance, while McWilliams and Siegel (2000) found that CSR has a neutral impact on corporate performance. Vogel (2005) noted that no decisive conclusion has been reached about the relevance of social responsibility to company revenue. It has not yet been proven whether more responsible action suits the self-interests of all companies or whether CSR always takes a margin of the profit. Moreover, the direction of the correlation between CSR and profit is undetermined. Financial success may be a cause of social responsibility or an effect. The various study results reported here suggest that there may be high potential for a positive relationship between CSR and corporate performance in general, but the relationship could be negative or the two could be unrelated. To date, there is no positive established theory.

Research Hypothesis

H1: There is significant relationship between the education initiative CSR and business Expansion.

H2: There is significant relationship between the Leadership program CSR and business Expansion.

H3: There is significant relationship between the financial literacy & access CSR and business Expansion.

H4: There is significant relationship between the agricultural support initiative CSR and business Expansion.

H5: There is significant relationship between the environmental protection initiative CSR and business Expansion.

Based on these hypotheses, here below is a conceptual framework (see Figure 3.1) that shows the relationship between dependent variable (consumer choice behavior) and its attributes factors.

Figure3.1 Conceptual Framework (Source: Organized by the current thesis)

Source of Data

Primary data

Primary sources are original Works of research , It Is considered as raw data without interpretation or pronouncements that represent an official opinion or position, it shelters memos, letters, complete interviews or speeches, laws and regulations, government data and so on. Primary sources are examined as the most authoritative since the information has not been filtered or explicated by the second party (Cooper & Schindler, 2003). This kind of data cannot be answered and explained in secondary data. There are so many ways to collect this data such as through interview, questionnaires, experiment, observation, and so on. This research will use quantitative research with the use of highly structured and rigid techniques like online questionnaires, mobile questionnaires, and telephone or chatting interview.

Secondary data

Secondary data already in existence was collected for some purpose other than the current study (Gillespie and Hennessey, 2010). Secondary sources have the main advantage that the material is readily available and it is so cheap and easy to use. There is no need to spend time and money collecting data, and some data, such as that provided by the census, would be impossible for an individual to collect (Browne, 2011). Secondary data sources can consist of company or government reports, archival data, advertisements, newspaper articles and books. This study will use the secondary data which have been collected and available from previous researchers or parties.

Data collecting method

The data collection method on this study is using a questionnaire. Questionnaire technique is a method of collecting marketing information directly from consumers. Sampling method will use convenient sampling method. Researcher will use online questionnaire because it will be more efficient and economist to distribute and contact the target respondents. Before distribute the questionnaires to target respondents, the researcher will do pilot test with invite some persons and teachers in order to analyze their understanding of the concept of sustainable and renewable energy and their vision in the trust of this new concept or the choice of conventional energy. Moreover, questionnaire translation into French and Arabic is compulsory, in order to avoid the misunderstanding of respondents who cannot understand English.

The target respondents must fulfill these criteria, such as:

1. Bangladeshi, female or male.
2. Age above 18 and above without any other condition on age since all adults are concerned about this topic.
3. What is your position in the organization?
4. How long have you worked with this organization?

The questionnaire will be spread in some big cities in Bangladesh, such as Dhaka, Chittagong, Khulna, etc. for one month. The target respondents of the researcher are amounted to 50 respondents.

Data instrument and questionnaires design

Questionnaire is a systematic list of questions which is sent to the respondents who answer these questions. A questionnaire consists of a schedule of questions sent by mail to the persons on a list or in a sample survey (Gupta and Gupta, 2011). Besides that, the primary data can be carried out as the main sources to analyze the Bangladeshi current situation when it comes to corporate social responsibility.

Questionnaires were personally administered by the researcher. The questionnaires contained a series of structured questions, which were related to the research and directed to respondents with the aim of gaining information and it is considered as the most commonly and easiest method, the anonymity (unnamed) will definitely enhance the validity while the structured questions will be clearly comparable and assessed between the subject groups (Graton & Jones, 2010).

For design questionnaires, this study will use closed ended questions which will be divided to three sections such as, section one contains demographic questions such as age, gender, occupation, marital status. Section 2 contains What criteria do you apply in selecting the beneficiaries of the education program?, Do you offer leadership programs to the organization’s stakeholders , and so on. Section 3 contains the impact of five variables which are functional value, social value, emotional value, epistemic value, conditional value on consumer choice behavior. Section 3 will be measured with seven-point Likert type scale ranging from 1: Strongly disagree to 5: Strongly agree.

Table 3. 1

Items Composing Consumer Behavior Determinant Attributes

Variables	Items		Total Items
Education Initiative	a. Grameen Shiksha Britti has been beneficial to most of our customers. b. All the beneficiaries of Grameen Shiksha Britti have been loyal customers c. The beneficiaries of Grameen Shiksha Britti have been a vocal marketing tool d. Most of the relatives and close friends of the education and leadership program beneficiaries have become loyal customers e. The Grameen Shiksha Britti of the bank has been vital for success in new markets .		(Question 1 to 5)
Leadership Program Initiative	a. The beneficiaries of Grameen Dialogue have been a vocal marketing tool for the bank.		(Question 6 to10)

Variables	Items		Total Items
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> b. Most of the relatives and close friends of the Grameen Dialogue Program beneficiaries have become loyal customers. c. The Grameen Dialogue program has provided a key source of talent. d. Involvement of Grameen Bank in Grameen Dialogue Program has made it easy to attract better employees. e. The Grameen Dialogue Program of the bank has been vital for bank’s success in new markets in the region. 		
Financial Literacy and Access Initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. The financial literacy and access skills are only offered to our customers or potential customers b. Most of the beneficiaries of the financial literacy and access skills programs are currently our customers and are loyal to the organization c. The financial literacy and access initiatives are created within our strategic focus on unbanked d. Through the bank’s financial literacy and access initiatives, it have been able to access a wider market base e. The cost incurred in carrying out financial literacy and access initiatives is less than the benefits realized 		(Question 11 to 15)
Environmental Conservation Initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. The bank offers environmental conservation where there shall be mutual benefit . b. The involvement of the bank in environmental conservation has helped it access a greater number of business partners regionally and globally. c. The environmental conservation initiatives have helped the bank to reach out to a wider number of customers. d. The environmental conservation initiatives have greatly enhanced the image of the bank among all stakeholders e. Became able to attract more investors 		(Question 16 to 20)

Variables	Items		Total Items
	and shareholders through the environmental conservation initiatives		
Agricultural Support Initiatives	a. The agricultural support initiatives are only offered to our customers & potential customers. b. All the beneficiaries of agricultural support are currently the bank customers and are loyal to the organization c. The bank is able to reach out to a wider customer base through the agricultural support initiatives. d. The agricultural support initiatives were created within the strategic focus on the unbanked. e. Through agricultural support initiatives the organization has been able to grow the income of their customers hence creating more business for the Bank.		(Question 21 to 25)
Business Expansion	a. Firm has lately bought in new assets b. Return on Investment has increased . c. Customer base has increased d. Firm has low employee turn-over. e. Customers keep referring other people to us.		(Question 26 to 30)

(Source: Organized by the current thesis)

Data analysis technique

After gathering all of filled questionnaires from respondent targets, the researcher will process the questionnaires data with analysis data techniques. Data analysis techniques have important role in influencing a success of this research. All survey data which are collected through online questionnaires will be analysed with using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23. In order to achieve research objectives and test the hypothesis, different types of analysis were conducted including descriptive analysis, reliability, and multiple regression analysis. The definition and rule of thumb of each data analysis techniques will be explained below.

Descriptive analysis

Descriptive analysis can be defined as the transformation of raw data into a form that will make the reader easy to understand and interpret, rearrange, order, and manipulate data to generate descriptive information (Zikmund, W.G. 2003). This analysis is very important because it will help the researcher to visualize and simplify the lots number of raw data. Typically, there are two general types of statistics that are used to describe data such as measures of central tendency and measures of spread. The first type is the measures of central tendency that are ways of describing the central position of a frequency distribution for a group of data. The researcher can use a number of statistics such as

mode, median, and mean to describe this central position. The second type is measures of spreading the ways of summarizing a group of data by describing how to spread out the scores. To describe this spread, a number of statistics are available such as range, quartiles, absolute deviation, variance, and standard deviation.

Validity analysis

Bryman and Bell (2007) mentioned that questionnaires are referred to always lack validity for many reasons. Validity is a degree to which an instrument or test measures what it needs to measure can be classified as content, criterion, logical or construct validity. Similarly Myers (2009) has mentioned that validity of measurement denotes the degree to which the scores from the test or instrument measures what it is supposed to measure.

Reliability analysis

Reliability can be defined as the degree of measures to generate consistent results (Zikmund et al., 2011). This analysis ensures that data collection is accurate and consistent. Reliability signifies the internal consistency of the items that were developed to measure specific construct with a high level of reliability. The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient is the most frequently used to calculate internal reliability of each variable and construct. There are two version of alpha: the normal and the standardized version. The normal alpha can be used when items on a scale are summed to produce single score for that scale, whereas the standardized alpha is useful when items on a scale are standardized before being summed. George and Mallery (2003) provided an accepted empirical rule to explain the internal consistency. The internal consistency is excellent when the value is between 0.9 and 1.0, it is good when the value is between 0.8 and 0.9, when it is between 0.7 and 0.8, it is acceptable. According to Maholtra (2007), the reliability acceptance level should be more than 0.6.

Inferential statistic - Multiple regression analysis

The research method used is multiple linear regressions. Multiple linear regression was used to determine the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable, where the independent variables consist of two or more (Lind et al, 2014). This study uses multiple linear regression analysis because this study aims to determine the influence of independent variables on dependent variable, namely purchase intention or consumer choice behavior. Multiple regression formulation is:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \epsilon$$

Information:

Y : Business Expansion

α : Constants

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$: Regression Coefficients

X1, X2, X3, X4 : Independent variables

ϵ : Residual

Multiple correlation coefficients (R) are the level of the relationship between independent variables with the dependent variable. The value of R lies between -1 to 1. If R is close to 1, it can be said that has a positive relationship very tightly, and vice versa. According Lind et al (2014), the coefficient of determination (R^2) is used to measure how far the ability of the model to explain variations dependent variable. Small value of R^2 , which means the ability of the independent variables in explaining the variation in the dependent variable, is very limited.

Data analysis

Introduction

This chapter discusses the role of corporate social responsibility(CSR) on business expansion of Grameen Bank according to the standpoints of the 50 respondents of Grameen Bank surveyed in the study. To achieve this, the present chapter is organized in three sections where; the first most section quickly summarizes the general description of the surveyed respondents in terms of their overall characteristics such as: age categories, education level, Time of interaction and so on. The second section will then follow to explicitly examine the validity and reliability of the test of the questionnaire used along the research in order to see if the construct is credible or not. The third section will then continue to analyze the role of corporate social responsibility(CSR) on business expansion of Grameen Bank using the technique of the multiple linear regression in order to prove whether the factors mentioned in the previous have positive or negative relationship with the business expansion of Grameen Bank.

4.2 Descriptive Analysis

As explained in the previous chapter, descriptive analysis can be used to make it easier for the reader to read and conclude if there are lots of data. In the research, total respondents which are used to process the data is amounted to 50 respondents.

Descriptive analysis of demographic.

1. Age categories

Table 4. 1

Age of Respondent

Age	Frequency	Percent
19-28 years old	17	34.0
29-38 years old	18	36.0
39-48 years old	11	22.0
> 48 years old	4	8.0
Total	50	100.0

(Source: Organized by the current thesis)

Figure 4. 1Age of Respondent (Source: Organized by the current thesis)

The figure 4.2 portrays a representation of the age distribution of the sample. It is observed that most of the respondents of the sample which is amounted to 50 respondents are in the age category of 29– 38 years old (n=18 or 36.0%), closely followed by the age category 19-28years old (n=17 or 34.0%). This is followed by the age category 39-48 years old (n=11 or 22.0%), which is followed by the least amount of respondents in the which is age category 48 years old and above (n=4 or 8.0%).

2. Gender

Table 4. 2

Gender of Respondent		
Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	37	74.0
Female	13	26.0
Total	50	100.0

(Source: Organized by the current thesis)

Figure 4. 2 Gender of Respondent (Source: Organized by the current thesis)

The pie representation below (Figure 4.2) represents the gender of the sample which is amounted to 50 respondents. It is evident that the population was primarily representative of male employees to that of female employees. The male respondents comprised of 74% (n=37) while female respondents comprised of 26% (n=13).

3. Position in Organization

Table 4. 3

Respondent Position in Organization

Occupation	Frequency	Percent
Branch Manager	22	44.0
Assistant Manager	13	26.0
Supervisor	9	18.0
Staff	6	12.0
Total	50	100.0

(Source: Organized by the current thesis)

Figure 4. 3 Position in the organization of Respondent (Source: Organized by the current thesis)

Table 4.3 and figure 4.3 show that most of the respondents' position in the organization is branch manager which is amounted to 22 respondents (44.0% from the total respondents), followed by respondent assistant manager and they are amounted to 13 respondents (26.0%). Only 9 respondents (18.0%) are Supervisor and 6 respondents (12.0%) are staff.

4. Education Level

Table 4. 4

Respondent Education Level

Education level	Frequency	Percent
Post Graduate	26	52.0
Graduate	12	24.0
Diploma	7	14.0
Certificate	5	10.0
Total	50	100.0

(Source: Organized by the current thesis)

Figure 4. 4 Occupation of Respondent (Source: Organized by the current thesis)

Table 4.4 and figure 4.4 shows that most of the respondents’ education level is post graduate which is amounted to 26 respondents (52.0% from the total respondents), followed by graduate and they are amounted to 12 respondents (24.0%). Only 7 respondents (18.0%) education level are diploma and 5 respondents (10.0%) education level are certificate examination.

Descriptive analysis of variable

Descriptive analysis aims to describe respondents’ characteristics and respondents’ answers toward the questions in the questionnaires for each variable. The variables in this research are Education Initiative(X_1), Leadership Program (X_2), Financial literacy & Access (X_3), Agricultural Support Initiative (X_4), Environmental Protection Initiative (X_5), and Business Expansion (Y).

The respondents’ answer images are gotten from the total intervals of class means, by making scale ranges, in order to know the mean positions of respondents’ evaluations toward each variable questioned. The examples of mean scale ranges are showed as follows:

- 1,00 - < 1,80 = Very Disagreed
- 1,81 - < 2,60 = Disagreed
- 2,61 - < 3,40 = Hesitated
- 3,41 - < 4,20 = Agreed
- 4,21 - < 5,00 = Very Agreed

As explained in the variable operational definitions in the research, they are Education Initiative(X_1), Leadership Program (X_2), Financial literacy & Access (X_3), Agricultural Support Initiative (X_4), Environmental Protection Initiative (X_5), and Business Expansion (Y) showed as follows:

a. Variable Descriptive Analysis of Education Initiative(X_1)

As explained in the definition of Education Initiative(X_1), it is one of independent variables with several indicators showed in Table 4.5 as follows:

Table 4. 5

The Respondent Response Results Toward Variable of Education Initiative(X_1)

Number	Indicator	Mean
1	Grameen Shiksa Britti has been beneficial to most of our customers.	3.60
2	All the beneficiaries of Grameen Shiksa Britti have been loyal customers	3.54
3	The beneficiaries of Grameen Shiksa Britti have been a vocal marketing too	3.56
4	Most of the relatives and close friends of the education program beneficiaries have become loyal customers	3.64
5	The Grameen Shiksa Britti of the bank has been vital for success in new markets	3.52
The Variable Mean of <i>Education Initiative</i> (X_1)		3.572

(Source: Organized by the current thesis)

Based on the Table above, it shows that the majority from 50 respondents give the evaluation as Agreed by having the highest mean value of 3.64 available in indicator $X_{1.4}$ by stating that “Most of the relatives and close friends of the education program beneficiaries have become loyal customers”. Whereas generally, the variable statement of *Education Initiative*(X_1)has the mean value from the respondents of 3.56 which means that the respondents give the evaluation as **agreed** about the relationship between the Education initiative CSR and its role on business expansion .

Descriptive analysis of Leadership program (X_2)

As explained in the definition of leadership program (X_2), it is one of independent variables with several indicators showed in Table 4.6 as follows:

Table 4. 6

The Respondent Response Results Toward Variable of leadership program (X_2)

Number	Indicator	Mean
1.	The beneficiaries of Grameen Dialogue have been a vocal marketing tool for the bank.	3.48
2.	Most of the relatives and close friends of the Grameen Dialogue Program beneficiaries have become loyal customers.	3.50
3.	The Grameen Dialogue program has provided a key source of talent.	3.56
4.	Involvement of Grameen Bank in Grameen Dialogue Program has made it easy to attract better employees.	3.46
5.	The Grameen Dialogue Program of the bank has been vital for bank’s success in new markets in the region.	3.52
The Variable Mean of <i>leadership program</i> (X_2)		3.504

(Source: Organized by the current thesis)

Based on the Table above, it shows that the majority from 50 respondents in the variable of leadership program (X_2) give the evaluation as Agreed by the total highest mean value of 3.56 available in indicator $X_{2.3}$ by stating that “The Grameen Dialogue program has provided a key source of talent.”. Whereas, generally the variable statementof leadership program (X_2) achieves the mean value from the respondents of 3.504 which means that the respondents give the evaluation as **agreed** about the relationship between the leadership program and its role on business expansion.

Variable descriptive analysis of financial literacy and access initiatives (X₃)

As explained in the definition of *Financial Literacy and Access Initiatives* (X₃), it is a dependent variable with several indicators showed in Table 4.7:

Table 4. 7

Respondent Response Results Toward Variable of Financial Literacy and Access Initiatives (X₃)

Number	Indicator	Mean
1.	The financial literacy and access skills are only offered to our customers or potential customers	3.32
2.	Most of the beneficiaries of the financial literacy and access skills programs are currently our customers and are loyal to the organization	3.22
3.	Through the bank’s financial literacy and access initiatives, it have been able to access a wider market base	3.40
4.	The financial literacy and access initiatives are created within our strategic focus on unbanked	3.24
5.	The cost incurred in carrying out financial literacy and access initiatives is less than the benefits realized	3.38
The Variable Mean of Financial Literacy and Access Initiatives (X ₃)		3.312

(Source: Organized by the current thesis)

Based on the Table above, it shows that the majority from 50 respondents give the evaluation as **Agreed** by the total ones having the highest mean value of 3.40 available in indicator X_{3.3} by stating that “Through the bank’s financial literacy and access initiatives, it have been able to access a wider market base” Whereas, generally the variable statement of Financial Literacy and Access Initiatives achieves the mean value from the respondents of 3.312 which means that the respondents give the evaluation as **Hesitated** about the relationship between the Financial Literacy and Access Initiatives CSR and its role on business expansion of Grameen Bank.

Variable descriptive analysis of environmental conservation initiatives (X₄)

As explained in the definition of *Environmental Conservation Initiatives* (X₄), it is a dependent variable with several indicators showed in Table 4.8:

Table 4. 8

Respondent Response Results Toward Variable of *Environmental Conservation Initiatives* (X₄)

Number	Indicator	Mean
1.	The bank offers environmental conservation where there shall be mutual benefit	3.46
2.	The involvement of the bank in environmental conservation has helped it access a greater number of business partners regionally and globally	3.44
3.	The environmental conservation initiatives have helped the bank to reach out to a wider number of customers	3.46

4.	Being environmentally friendly has wooed many customers into the institution with most becoming loyal	3.48
5.	The environmental conservation initiatives have greatly enhanced the image of the bank among all stakeholders	3.50
The Variable Mean of <i>Environmental Conservation Initiatives</i> (X ₄)		3.468

(Source: Organized by the current thesis)

Based on the Table above, it shows that the majority from 50 respondents give the evaluation as Agreed by the total ones having the highest mean value of 3.50 available in indicator X_{4.5} by stating “ Through agricultural support initiatives, we have been able to attract more shareholders/ investors.” Whereas, generally the variable statement of Environmental Conservation Initiatives achieves the mean value from the respondents of 3.468 which means that the respondents give the evaluation as **agreed** about the relationship between the Environmental Conservation Initiatives and its role on business expansion of Grameen Bank.

Variable descriptive analysis of Agricultural support initiatives (X₅)

As explained in the definition of Agricultural Support Initiatives (X₅), it is a dependent variable with several indicators showed in Table 4.9:

Table 4. 9

The Respondent Response Results Toward Variable of *Conditional Value*(X₅)

Number	Indicator	Mean
1.	The agricultural support initiatives are only offered to our customers & potential customers.	3.52
2.	The agricultural support initiatives were created within the strategic focus on the unbanked.	3.34
3.	The bank is able to reach out to a wider customer base through the agricultural support initiatives.	3.54
4.	All the beneficiaries of agricultural support are currently the bank customers and are loyal to the organization	3.60
5.	Through agricultural support initiatives, we have been able to attract more shareholders/ investors	3.38
The Variable Mean of Agricultural Support Initiatives (X ₅)		3.476

(Source: Organized by the current thesis)

Based on the Table above, it shows that the majority from 50 respondents give the evaluation as Agreed by the total ones having the highest mean value of 3.60 available in indicator X_{5.4} by stating: “ All the beneficiaries of agricultural support are currently the bank customers and are loyal to the organization.” Whereas, generally the variable statement of Agricultural Support Initiatives achieves the mean value from the respondents of 3.476 which means that the respondents give the evaluation as **Agreed** about the relationship between the Agricultural Support Initiatives and its role on business expansion of Grameen Bank

Variable Descriptive Analysis of Business Expansion (Y)

As explained in the definition of *Business Expansion* (Y), it is the independent variable with several indicators showed in Table 4.10:

Table 4. 10

The Respondent Response Results Toward Variable of *Business Expansion* (Y)

Number	Indicator	Mean
1.	Firm has lately bought in new assets.	3.44
2.	Return on Investment has increased .	3.64
3.	Customer base has increased.	3.62
4.	Firm has low employee turn-over.	3.46
5.	Customers keep referring other people to us.	3.62
The Variable Mean of <i>Business Expansion</i> (Y)		3.556

(Source: Organized by the current thesis)

Based on the Table above, it shows that the majority from 50 respondents give the evaluation as Agreed by having the highest mean value of 3.64 available in indicator Y₂ by stating: “Return on Investment has increased “. Whereas, generally the variable statement of *Business Expansion* achieves the mean value from the respondents of 3.556 which means that the respondents give the evaluation as **Agreed**.

Validity and reliability test

Validity Test

Validity testing is done to measure the validity of a questionnaire. The results of the analysis are sig values compared to the significant level of 0.05. To simplify the analysis, we use the SPSS program computer assistance. The following are the results of testing the validity by calculating the Pearson Product Moment correlation coefficient.

Table 4. 11

Validity Test

Item	Coefficient Correlation	Sig	Conclusion
Education Initiatives (X ₁)			
X _{1.1}	0.683	0.000	Valid
X _{1.2}	0.706	0.000	Valid
X _{1.3}	0.447	0.000	Valid
X _{1.4}	0.668	0.000	Valid
X _{1.5}	0.700	0.000	Valid
Leadership program (X ₂)			

Item	Coefficient Correlation	Sig	Conclusion
X _{2.1}	0.634	0.000	Valid
X _{2.2}	0.717	0.000	Valid
X _{2.3}	0.498	0.000	Valid
X _{2.4}	0.625	0.000	Valid
X _{2.5}	0.705	0.00	Valid
Financial Literacy and Access Initiatives (X ₃)			
X _{3.1}	0.764	0.000	Valid
X _{3.2}	0.789	0.000	Valid
X _{3.3}	0.714	0.000	Valid
X _{3.4}	0.762	0.000	Valid
X _{3.5}	0.698	0.00	Valid
Environmental Conservation Initiatives (X ₄)			
X _{4.1}	0.657	0.008	Valid
X _{4.2}	0.691	0.000	Valid
X _{4.3}	0.500	0.000	Valid
X _{4.4}	0.622	0.000	Valid
X _{4.5}	0.720	0.00	Valid
Agricultural Support Initiatives (X ₅)			
X _{5.1}	0.715	0.000	Valid
X _{5.2}	0.774	0.000	Valid
X _{5.3}	0.676	0.000	Valid
X _{5.4}	0.774	0.000	Valid
X _{4.5}	0.760	0.00	Valid
Business Expansion (Y)			
Y ₁	0.724	0.000	Valid

Item	Coefficient Correlation	Sig	Conclusion
Y ₂	0.787	0.000	Valid
Y ₃	0.440	0.000	Valid
Y ₄	0.788	0.000	Valid
Y ₅	0.806	0.000	Valid

(Source: Organized by the current thesis)

Reliability Test

The construct reliability test was carried out to measure if the construct is reliable or not. It is reliable if Cronbach Alpha > 0.6, following the results of reliability testing:

Table 4. 12

Reliability Test

Variable	Alpha	Conclusion
Education Initiative (X ₁)	0.639	Reliable
Leadership Program (X ₂)	0.632	Reliable
Financial Literacy and Access Initiatives (X ₃)	0.866	Reliable
Environmental Conservation Initiatives (X ₄)	0.756	Reliable
Agricultural Support Initiatives (X ₅)	0.789	Reliable
Business Expansion (Y)	0.841	Reliable

(Source: Organized by the current thesis)

Based on Table 4.12 above, it shows that the reliability examination results in all variables show as reliable entirely, because the value of Cronbach's Alpha is higher than 0.6 so it is stated that all indicators are reliable.

Multiple Regression Analysis

Figure 4. 5 Regression Model (Source: Organized by the current thesis)

Multiple linear regression similarity

The data analysis used in this research is multiple linear regression used for knowing whether there are influences of Education Initiative (X_1), Leadership Program (X_2), Financial Literacy and Access Initiatives (X_3), Environmental Conservation Initiatives (X_4), Agricultural Support Initiatives (X_5) toward *Business Expansion* or not. Based on the data processing calculational results by the program computer aid of SPSS 25.00 for windows, so it is achieved the significant multiple linear regression as follows:

$$Y = -2.031 + 0.424 X_1 + 0.305 X_2 + 0.216 X_3 + 0.407 X_4 + 0.252 X_5$$

Table 4. 13

Coefficients of the multiple linear regression

		Coefficients ^a				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	-2.031	.616		-3.298	.002
	Education	.424	.156	.342	2.715	.009
	Leadership	.305	.113	.236	2.708	.010
	Financial	.216	.078	.236	2.769	.008
	Environment	.407	.106	.333	3.857	.000
	Agriculture	.252	.116	.268	2.180	.035

a. Dependent Variable: Business Expansion.

(Source: Organized by the current thesis)

The statistical significance of each of the independent variables can be tested. This allows to test whether the unstandardized (or standardized) coefficients are equal to 0 (zero) in the population.

Unstandardized coefficients indicate how much the dependent variable varies with an independent variable when all other independent variables are held constant. Looking at the result of each item, we can make the following conclusions :

- Constant (a) resulted is -2.031, that shows that the total value of Business expansion (Y) is -2.031 if Education Initiative (X₁), Leadership Program (X₂), Financial Literacy and Access Initiatives (X₃), Environmental Conservation Initiatives (X₄), Agricultural Support Initiatives (X₅) are constant.
- The coefficient value of Education Initiative (β_1) is 0.424 and it shows that if the variable of Education Initiative (β_1) increases by one unit, there will be an increase in *Business Expansion* by 0.424 units with the assumption that the other variables are constant. We can see from the results that the coefficient related to the Education Initiative is the highest one, which means that, in our study, it's the factor that influences the **most** the variation of the business expansion.
- The coefficient value of Leadership Program (β_2) is 0.305, it means that there is a positive relationship between the business expansion and the Leadership Program. It also shows that if the variable of Leadership Program (β_2) increases by one unit, there will be an increase of *business expansion* by 0.305 units with the assumption that the other variables are constant.
- The coefficient value of Financial Literacy and Access Initiatives (β_3) is 0.216. The relationship between the variables is negative as well and it shows that if the variable of Financial Literacy and Access Initiatives (β_3) increases by one unit, there will an decrease of *business expansion* by 0.216 units, by the assumption that the other variables are constant.
- The coefficient value of Environmental Conservation Initiatives (β_4) is 0.407 and shows that if the variable of Environmental Conservation Initiatives (β_4) increases by one unit, there will be an increase in *business expansion* by 0.407 units with the assumption that the other variables are constant.
- The coefficient value of Agricultural Support Initiatives (β_5) is 0.252 and shows that if the variable of Agricultural Support Initiatives (β_5) increases by one unit, it will cause the increase of *Business Expansion* by 0.252 units, with the assumption that the other variables are constant.

Correlational coefficient analysis (R) And Determination coefficient (R²)

Table 4. 14

R Square Test

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.841 ^a	.707	.674	.29038
a. Predictors: (Constant), Agriculture, Financial, Environment, Leadership, Education				

The correlational coefficient value (R) shows about how close are the relations between independent variables (Education Initiative (X₁), Leadership Program (X₂), Financial Literacy and Access Initiatives (X₃), Environmental Conservation Initiatives (X₄), Agricultural Support Initiatives (X₅), and dependent variable (*Business Expansion*). The total correlational coefficient value is 0.841. The value shows that the variable relations of Education Initiative (X₁), Leadership Program (X₂), Financial Literacy and Access Initiatives (X₃), Environmental Conservation Initiatives (X₄),

Agricultural Support Initiatives (X_5) and variable of *Business Expansion* are very strong (strong association) because the correlational value is positioned between 0.8 and 1.

The determination coefficient value or R^2 is used for measuring to what extent the model abilities in explaining dependent variable variations of *Business Expansion* (Y). From the results of SPSS calculations, it is achieved that the value of $R^2 = 0.707$ that means that 70.7% of *CSR based business expansion* can be explained by variables of Education Initiative (X_1), Leadership Program (X_2), Financial Literacy and Access Initiatives (X_3), Environmental Conservation Initiatives (X_4), Agricultural Support Initiatives (X_5).

Hypothesis examination

In reference to the the problem previously stated and the research hypothesis proposed, it can be explained that the variables that influence Performance are Education Initiative (X_1), Leadership Program (X_2), Financial Literacy and Access Initiatives (X_3), Environmental Conservation Initiatives (X_4), Agricultural Support Initiatives (X_5) and the dependent variable of this research is *Business Expansion*, i.e variable Y.

Test t aims to expose whether the independent variables influence partially the *Business Expansion*. If the results show a significant value <0.05 , it means that the independent variables partially influence the dependent variable.

Table 4. 5

Paired Sample Correlation Test					
Paired Samples Correlations					
		N	Correlation	Sig.	
Pair 1	BusinessExpansion & Education	50	0.707	0.000	
Pair 2	Business Expansion & Leadership	50	0.333	0.018	
Pair 3	Business Expansion & Financial	50	0.353	0.012	

T-test (partial) on education initiative (X_1):

Based on the calculational results of SPSS, the independent variable significance value of Education Initiatives (X_1) in t-test is 0.000 or < 0.05 . This case shows that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. So, There is significant relationship between the education initiative CSR and business Expansion .

T-test (partial) on leadership program (X_2):

Based on the calculational results of SPSS, the independent variable significance value of Leadership Program (X_2) in t-test is 0.018 or < 0.05 . This case shows that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. So, There is significant relationship between the Leadership program initiative and business Expansion.

T-test (partial) on financial literacy and access initiatives (X_3):

Based on the calculational results of SPSS, the independent variable significance value of Financial Literacy and Access Initiatives (X_3) in t-test is .012 or < 0.05 . This case shows that H_1 is accepted and H_0 is rejected. So, There is significant relationship between the financial literacy & access CSR and business Expansion.

T-test (partial) on agricultural support initiatives (X_4):

Based on the calculational results of SPSS, the independent variable significance value of Agricultural Support Initiatives (X4) in t-test 0.004 or < 0.05 . This case shows that H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted. So There is significant relationship between the agricultural support initiative CSR and business Expansion.

T-test (partial) on agricultural support initiatives (X5):

Based on the calculational results of SPSS, the independent variable significance value of Agricultural Support Initiatives (X5) in t-test is 0.000 or < 0.05 . This case shows that H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted. So, There is significant relationship between the environmental protection initiative CSR and business Expansion.

Analysis of results

Based on the hypothesis examinational results using partial test (T-test), it is achieved that Education Initiative (X1) has influences toward *Business Expansion* (Y). This case can be shown from the significance value in the variable in test t of Education Initiative (X1) as it shows a value of 0.000 which is smaller than *level of significance* (α) of 0,05. Based on these findings, the first hypothesis that states "There is significant relationship between the education initiative CSR and business Expansion." is proven as true and acceptable.

The analysis results show that there is an influence of the Education Initiative towards the *Business Expansion*. It means that the higher is the Education initiative CSR, the more the *Business expansion*.

Similarly, and following the same logic, the hypothesis examination results after using partial test (T-test) on the other variables which are *Leadership Program* (X2), *Financial Literacy and Access Initiatives* (X3), *Environmental Conservation Initiatives* (X4), *Agricultural Support Initiatives* (X5) lead us to make the following conclusions:

The results of test t show for the four variables *Leadership Program* (X2), *Financial Literacy and Access Initiatives* (X3), *Environmental Conservation Initiatives* (X4), *Agricultural Support Initiatives* (X5) a value inferior to 0,05 which means that these variables have an influence on the dependent variable *Business Expansion* (Y). As a conclusion, we can state that:

- "There is significant relationship between the Leadership Program Initiative and Business Expansion" is proven as true and acceptable.
- "There is significant relationship between the *Financial Literacy and Access Initiatives* and Business Expansion" is proven as true and acceptable.

Discussion and recommendations

Discussion of the main findings

The study found that education CSR initiatives were offered from the secondary level to the tertiary level of education with the main recruitment method being from special groups such as poor but talented students or excessively bright students. The study found that education CSR impacts the firm operations as it is beneficial to most of their customers, beneficiaries become loyal customers to the bank, beneficiaries become vocal marketing agents for the bank, people close to beneficiaries join the institution, ease entry to new markets, align to firm's Expansion strategy, and the cost of the initiative is moderately less than the accrued benefits in the long run. Similar observations were made for the leadership CSR initiatives offered by the financial institution with one key contribution being Leadership Program that was said to have provided the institution with a key source of talent for the company hence reducing recruitment costs, cheaper marketing medium, increased market base, improved and talented employee base, and strategic support to the company.

The study further confirmed that financial access and literacy have an impact within Grameen bank and is perceived by the beneficiaries as being important to bank operations with the bank benefiting from a widened market base from the beneficiaries, eased marketing channels, new markets and higher benefits than the costs incurred in the

undertakings. Similar views for environmental conservation initiatives and agricultural support were realized in the study with the beneficiaries and key informants observing that the initiatives have been very pivotal in the new markets accessed by the bank and increased market base where the bank is able to „bank the unbanked“. The study found that the financial institution has been performing exceptionally well within the last decade with the observations that the bank has been involved in purchase of new assets, improved net profits, Expansion in sales, ability to repay debts, increasing return on investment, growing sales, quick response system to customer complaints, dedicated customer service personnel, getting referrals, customers are satisfied, services are very reliable, low employee turn-over, and good relationship between management and employees. Therefore it can be confirmed that corporate social responsibility undertaken by Grameen Bank has a direct influence on the institution’s organization Expansion.

Conclusion, Research Limitations and Future Research

Conclusion

The discussion of the findings is in relation with the objectives of the study. It has found that the Views from respondents indicated that, CSR activities performed by Grameen Bank Education Initiative , Leadership Program , Financial Literacy and Access Initiatives , Environmental Conservation Initiatives , Agricultural Support Initiatives and these are very significant CSR activities that are helping Grameen bank for the expansion. This study sought to assess the link between CSR activities of a firm and organizational Expansion. The study objectives were to assess the influence of education and leadership CSR initiatives, financial access and literacy initiatives, environmental conservation initiatives, and agricultural support initiatives on the Expansion of Grameen Bank. The study sought to find the link between education and leadership CSR initiatives on the Expansion of the bank. Education and leadership training projects feed the society with skilled workforce from whom organizations source talent and which allows the firms to have access to highly productive workforce that has the capability to boost Expansion (Harteis, 2012). Abishua (2010) observed that Grameen Bank sources its talent through education CSR project, though the study has found more impacts of the initiatives on the institution such as customer base extension and loyalty, ease entry to new markets, alignment to firm’s Expansion strategy, and cost of the initiative being lower than the accrued benefits in the long run. Khana & Afzalb, (2011) claimed that education and leadership CSR enhance organizational competitiveness and performance, by fostering the core values such as performance excellence, innovation, social responsibility, worker involvement, and quality of work life among the institution employees and customers hence enhancing the firm position within a given market, which ultimately impact organization Expansion. The study therefore concludes that involvement in education and leadership programs at Grameen Bank has significantly influenced the bank Expansion.

The study looked at the link between environmental conservation initiatives and the Expansion of the involved institutions. According to Baron (2007), some investors prefer to make their social donations through investing in socially responsible companies; involvement in CSR can increase the value of the firm by attracting these investors. Graff and Small (2005), claims that the value of the firm is less than it would be without CSR, as this is a key source of value, customer loyalty and attraction of investors, allowing firms to grow in this environment. The study therefore concludes that the environmental conservation initiatives influence the Expansion of Grameen Bank.

The study further sought to assess the influence of agricultural CSR initiatives on Expansion of Grameen Bank. It was found that agricultural support initiatives have been very pivotal in the Expansion of the bank. These findings were earlier observed by Wang, et al., (2009), who observed that financial organizations directly benefit with direct marketing to the farmers, improved company image, better publicity, Expansion in customers and gains in profits gained from increase in business from the farmers. Juma (2011) also argue that agricultural support enhances productivity in agriculture raising farm incomes and reducing poverty of farming households, hence enhancing savings capacity and hence allowing the bank more incomes from the empowered farmer, hence raising capacity. It is therefore clear that agricultural CSR initiatives have significant influence on the Expansion of Grameen Bank.

Research limitations

Similarly to any other research, this paper has its own limitations that should not be ignored when guiding a study for future research. Firstly, the results of this study are based on a survey that covered 50 people only, which means that the results cannot be generalized on a wider population. Furthermore, this study was limited to a sample drawn from big cities only in Bangladesh, such as Dhaka, Khulna, and Chittagong. By expanding it to other cities and provinces, including rural populations, it will help to develop deeper and broader understandings and it will help with interpreting the function of CSR and Business Expansion.

Future research

This study only dwelt in one organization operating within a single industry-the banking industry. This study therefore suggests that further studies ought to be done in other sectors and companies to ascertain these findings and enhance future comprehension of the importance of CSR in organizations. Similar studies should also be done in other regions of the world to globalize these findings.

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